

PHYSICOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS, ACCEPTABILITY AND MARKETABILITY OF MABEANBRAN DINNER ROLL

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Physicochemical Analysis, Acceptability and Marketability of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the physicochemical analysis, the level of acceptability and marketability of 10 grams, 15 grams, and 20 grams proportions of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in Carranglan Nueva Ecija during the school year 2023-2024. The experimental method of research was used with survey questionnaire as the data gathering instrument. This study also used the nine Hedonic rating scale for the acceptability and five Likert scale for the marketability of the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll. Bakers, Consumers, and Sellers evaluated the acceptability and marketability of this research. The statistical tools used in the study were Weighted Mean, one-way ANOVA and Tukey Pairwise Comparison. The data revealed that the three groups of respondents evaluated the acceptability level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 10 grams, 15 grams, and 20 grams proportion in terms of appearance, aroma, color, taste, and texture as Very Acceptable. Meanwhile, there were no significant differences on the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in three proportions in terms of the said criteria. On the other hand, the level of marketability as evaluated by bakers, consumers, and sellers received different evaluations utilizing the 10 grams, 15 grams, and 20 grams in terms of supply availability, production cost, consumer demand, and packaging resulting to significant difference on their evaluations. Furthermore, the respondents provided comments and suggestion for further improvement of the product.

Keywords: *acceptability, marketability, physicochemical analysis, dinner roll*

Introduction

Dinner roll is a type of bread prepared into a small round loaf often served as a side to a meal. Dating back to ancient times, dinner rolls are named for their original purpose as an easily passed dinner food. Rice bran is a by-product of rice milling process turning out the polished white rice that one brings at the grocery store. That is to say that rice bran is what is left over from polishing brown rice into white rice.

According to the article from food.ndtv.com (2019), Rice Bran is used for treating diabetes, high blood pressure, high cholesterol, alcoholism, obesity, and aids. And for preventing stomach and colon cancer, preventing heart and blood vessels disease, also for strengthening the immune system, and improving athletic performance.

These ingredients are very economical because it can be grown in the country. Also, it easily gets the attention of the people because it mainly concerns the health and promotes a healthy lifestyle. Moringa oleifera or Malunggay is a fast-growing drought resistant tree of the family Moringaceae. It is widely cultivated for its young seed pods and leaves used as vegetables and for traditional herbal medicine. It is also used for water purification. Malunggay is one of the world's most useful plants. It is an important tree crop in many countries in Asia, Africa, Central and South America.

According to the article from National Nutrition Council (2022), Moringa oleifera or Malunggay may also help to lower blood sugar levels and it contains calcium and phosphorus which aid in the maintenance of healthy and strong bones. Along with its anti-inflammatory properties, moringa extract may aid in the treatment of conditions such as arthritis and it can also lower your cholesterol levels, potentially reducing the risk of heart disease.

On the other hand, Mung beans are one of the food ingredients that contain in high protein content. The nutritional content in mung beans is carbohydrates 56.8%, fat 1.5%, protein 22.9%, fiber 7.5%, water 15.5%, and ash 3.3%. Mung beans have the potential to be added as a source of protein in food products. Summer Moong is a short duration mung bean pulse crop grown in northern India. Due to its short duration, it can fit well in between of many cropping systems.

The main occupation of the people in Carranglan Nueva Ecija is in the rice fields and agriculture. Rice, malunggay and mung bean are the main crop in Carranglan. Rice bran is served as animal feed in Carranglan Nueva Ecija and even in our country. So, the researcher decided to come up with a study that rice bran, malunggay leaves and mung bean is also a great benefit for human health and nutrition and because of this observation the researcher decided to produce of dinner roll by adding rice bran, malunggay leaves and mung bean, so the researcher combined these three variables to make nutritious food. It is a dinner roll bread that consists of rice bran powder, malunggay leaves powder, and mung bean powder. The researcher called it as "MaBeanBran Dinner Roll".

It is more suitable and applicable for bakers, consumers, and sellers in Carranglan Nueva Ecija because it contains nutritious ingredients that can help to prevent common illnesses. By consuming MaBeanBran Dinner Roll it makes bakers, consumers, and sellers aware of the bread's health benefits and encourage them to adopt a healthy lifestyle. In addition to lowering the incidence of colon cancer and reducing heart and blood vessels illness, the researcher strongly suggests it for people with digestive tract issues.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the physicochemical analysis, the level of acceptability and marketability of 10 grams, 15 grams, and 20 grams proportions of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in Carranglan Nueva Ecija during the school year 2023-2024. More specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What was the physicochemical analysis of prepared MaBeanBran dinner roll in three different proportions in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. carbohydrates;
 - 1.2. moisture content
 - 1.3. ph level
 - 1.4. fats
 - 1.5. ash; and
 - 1.6. protein?
2. What was the evaluation of the bakers, consumers and sellers on the level of acceptability on the prepared MaBeanBran dinner roll in three different proportions in terms of the following criteria:
 - 2.1. appearance;
 - 2.2. aroma;
 - 2.3. color;
 - 2.4. taste; and
 - 2.5. texture?
3. Were there significant differences among the evaluations of the three groups of respondents on the level of acceptability of the prepared MaBeanBran dinner roll with rice bran, malunggay leaves, and mung bean powder in terms of the above-mentioned criteria?
4. What was the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the level of marketability of the prepared MaBeanBran dinner rolls in terms of the following aspects;
 - 4.1. supply availability;
 - 4.2. production cost;
 - 4.3. consumer demand; and
 - 4.4. packaging/labelling?
5. Were there significant differences among the evaluations of the three groups of respondents on the level of marketability of the rice bran powder, malunggay leaves powder, and mung bean powder in terms of the above cited criteria?
6. What comments and suggestions were offered by the three groups of respondents to further enhance the produced product?

Literature Review

An article in Czech Journal of Food Sciences (2023) entitled “Potential of Moringa Oleifera Leaf Powder for Functional Food Ingredients”. Based on this article, moringa leaf powder is a valuable source of protein, vitamins, minerals, and phytonutrients. Moringa is a plant that is found throughout many tropical nations. In this article, the impact of moringa leaf powder is also covered. Moringa leaf powder has a wide range of medicinal benefits, including those that are anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, hepatoprotective, cardioprotective, and antioxidant.

Kaminski (2022) posted in his article entitled “The Ultimate Bread Baking Guide: How to make Bread from Scratch”. It was highlighted how important it is to comprehend the advantages of using whole grains and wheat when making bread. Despite the variations in their sizes, colors, textures, and flavors, the several varieties of grains consumed as food have a lot in common. The makeup of all grains, which are the seeds of all plants, is essentially the same, but none of them should appear white when milled or processed as a whole due to the unique characteristics of the bran, germ, and endosperm. The article also underlined that bread can be served in a variety of ways at any meal of the day or consumed as a snack, with the bran consisting of the nutrient-rich layer covering the core kernel.

According to an article in Prime Nutrition Journal (2022) entitled “Sensory Quality of Brownies Substituted with Mung Bean Flour” emphasize that mung bean flour can be used to replace wheat flour in making brownies because mung bean contained high protein and high iron, calcium and vitamin A. In addition, mung bean flour has been shown to increase protein levels in cookies and vitamin A in pastries.

According to an article in Heliyon (2020) entitled “Biofortification of pulses and legumes to enhance nutrition” emphasize that pulses and legumes belong to the Fabaceae family which includes pulses and legumes including chickpeas, mungbeans, soybeans, and peas, is one of the most nutrient-dense. In many diets, pulses and legumes constitute a significant source of plant protein. They are also great sources of dietary fiber and complex carbs, which results in a low glycemic index. A good source of 15 necessary minerals and vitamins are also found in pulses and legumes. The nutritional benefits of mung beans, including its protein, carbs, fats, vitamins, minerals, and bioactive substances, are also highlighted in this article. Additionally, this site states that mung beans make up about 20–25% of the total dry weight and are a good source of protein. It has a high carbohydrate content of 50–65%. Mung beans have relatively little oil in them.

The study of Carag (2022) on “Acceptability and Marketability of Malunggay, Ampalaya, and Okra Seed Powder as a Coffee Substitute”. According on the findings of the study, that there was no significant difference in the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability and marketability of malunggay, ampalaya, and okra seed powder as a coffee substitute. The groups of respondents positively accepted the development of coffee.

Likewise, the study of Sakung et. al (2022), attempted to determine the “Saponins and Tannin Levels in Chayote, Mung Beans and Biscuits from Chayote and Mung Beans”. In this study the researcher used Gravimetric method to analyze and determine the level of saponins and tannins in biscuit made from chayote and mung bean. Therefore, the mung bean flour and mung bean biscuit, the saponin content was higher than chayote flour and chayote biscuit. The tannin content in formulation was derived from mung bean flour because the tannin content in mung bean was higher than chayote.

Moreover, Bartolome et. al (2023) entitled “Development and Acceptability of Process Taro Flour Supplemented with Bread Flour in Making Dinner Roll”. According on the findings of the study the dinner roll made with taro flour was accepted by respondents. From this study we can conclude that the product developed should be test by BFAD or Bureau of Food and Drugs to determine the content level of Taro Dinner Roll as to water content, ash content, protein, carbohydrate, calorie value and nutrient content.

Methodology

Research Design

To achieve its goal of determining the physicochemical analysis, acceptability, and marketability of the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 10 grams, 15 grams, and 20 grams of rice bran, malunggay leaves, and mung bean powder, the researcher used the experimental method of research.

According to Cash et al. (2016) in their book *Experimental Design Research: Approaches, Applications*, the Experimental method of research is the investigation of data based on the acquisition of reliable knowledge and documented observations under well-defined situations, using the proper statistical treatment and mathematical guidelines for the determination of possible relations.

Respondents

The data gathered in this research were from Carranglan Nueva Ecija. There were (30) thirty bakers, (30) thirty consumers and (30) thirty sellers as evaluators of the product presented.

Instruments

The data-gathering instrument that was used in this study was the presence of a survey questionnaire. This would make the evaluation of the three groups of respondents regarding the physicochemical analysis, the level of acceptability and marketability of Rice Bran, Malunggay Leaves, and Mung Bean Powder. There were five criteria being evaluated by the evaluator namely, bakers, consumers, and sellers in Barangay Bunga Carranglan, Nueva Ecija.

The following characteristics were utilized to assess the degree of acceptability: appearance, aroma, color, taste, and texture. A 9-point Hedonic Rating Scale with verbal interpretation was employed. The degree of marketability in terms of product cost, consumer demand, and supplier availability was assessed using a 5-point Likert rating scale.

Procedure

The researcher went through the following steps in gathering the needed data. First, the questionnaires were validated by some MPC FSM Professors. After the validation, through the help of the thesis adviser, the questionnaires were revised. Next, necessary communication letters were made. These letters were sent to the concerned recipients. Then, the prepared dinner roll samples were sent to laboratory testing for physicochemical analysis. After which, the survey-questionnaires together with the dinner roll samples in three proportions were administered to the respondents. Following the distribution and acquisition of survey questions, the investigator collected, tallied, and examined all the data required for the research investigation.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher herself explained and gave informed consent to each participant before the conduct of the study. She ensured them that the information would be used with utmost confidentiality and within the purpose of the study only.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings according to the study's research questions.

Physicochemical Analysis of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll

In a 200 grams sample, MaBeanBran Dinner Roll contains 60.3 carbohydrates, computed to classify it as a high-carbohydrates food product. With a moisture content of 18.8, the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll is considered to have low water activity. Furthermore, its potential of hydrogen (pH) value of 6.05 @ 22.5°C meets the standard regulations set by the U.S Department of Agriculture (USDA).

The fat content of 9.74/200g is relatively low, allowing MaBeanBran dinner roll to be claimed as "fat-free."

Additionally, the ash content, tested using ignition-gravimetry, revealed that the MaBeanBran dinner roll contains 1.07 g of ash, which is lower compared to other commercialized dinner roll. Lastly, the protein content at 10.1 implies that the protein content of the product falls within the range set by FNRI-DOST standards.

Table 1. Result of Physicochemical Analysis of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll

ANALYTE per 200g	RESULT	REFERENCE METHOD	DATE OF ANALYSIS	ANALYST
Carbohydrates	60.3	By computation	August 15, 2023 – September 4, 2023	G.M Maylas, A.F Guantia, P.T Baldoz, and D.M Ibug
Moisture	18.8	Vacuum Oven Drying	August 15, 2023 – September 4, 2023	G.M Maylas, A.F Guantia, P.T Baldoz, and D.M Ibug
pH (50% Dispersion)	6.05 @ 22.5 °C	Electrometry	August 15, 2023 – September 4, 2023	G.M Maylas, A.F Guantia, P.T Baldoz, and D.M Ibug
Fat	9.74	Acid Hydrolysis-Mojonnier Extraction	August 15, 2023 – September 4, 2023	G.M Maylas, A.F Guantia, P.T Baldoz, and D.M Ibug
Ash	1.07	Ignition-Gravimetry	August 15, 2023 – September 4, 2023	G.M Maylas, A.F Guantia, P.T Baldoz, and D.M Ibug
Protein (N X 6.25)	10.1	Kjeldahl	August 15, 2023 – September 4, 2023	G.M Maylas, A.F Guantia, P.T Baldoz, and D.M Ibug

Evaluation of Baker, Consumer and Seller Respondents on the Level of Acceptability of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 10g, 15g and 20g Proportions

Table 2. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 10 Grams Proportion as to Appearance

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The dinner rolls with rice bran and malunggay leaves powder is inviting to eat.	8.77	EA	8.70	EA	8.77	EA
2. It is fluffy.	8.67	EA	8.47	VA	8.30	VA
3. It has a smooth surface.	8.13	VA	8.40	VA	8.40	VA
4. It has uniform shape.	8.00	VA	8.47	VA	8.40	VA
5. It has a rounded top	8.00	VA	8.43	VA	8.43	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.31	VA	8.49	VA	8.46	VA

Based on the table, the Bakers, Consumers, and Sellers respondents rated the appearance with an overall weighted mean of 8.31, interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), 8.49 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA) and 8.46 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 10g proportion in indicators 1 to 2 were evaluated by the Baker respondents as Extremely Acceptable. For the consumer respondents, indicators 1 were interpreted as Extremely Acceptable.

Table 3. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 10 Grams Proportion as to Aroma

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The dinner roll with rice bran and malunggay leaves powder have lasting smell.	8.87	EA	8.83	EA	8.70	EA
2. It has ideal aroma of dinner roll.	8.47	VA	8.40	VA	8.53	EA
3. It has a pleasant smell.	8.37	VA	8.23	VA	8.33	VA
4. It has a desirable smell for dinner roll.	8.20	VA	8.33	VA	8.20	VA
5. It has enticing aroma.	7.77	VA	8.30	VA	8.27	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.33	VA	8.42	VA	8.41	VA

Based on the table, the Bakers, Consumers, and Sellers respondents rated the aroma with an overall weighted mean of 8.33, interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), 8.42 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA) and 8.41 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 10g proportion in indicator 1 when evaluated by the Baker respondents is Extremely Acceptable. For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. For the Seller respondents, indicators 1 and 2 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable.

Based on the table 4, the Bakers, Consumers and Sellers respondents rated the color with an overall weighted mean of 8.37 which was interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), 8.45 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA) and 8.58 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), respectively. For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1 and 4 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. For the Seller respondents, indicators 1, 3, and 4 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. The rest of the indicators when interpreted were found to be Very Acceptable.

Table 4. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 10 Grams Proportion as to Color

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. It has uniform color.	8.70	EA	8.67	EA	8.83	EA
2. It has golden brown outside	8.50	EA	8.23	VA	8.40	VA
3. The dinner roll with rice bran and malunggay leaves powder are visually attractive.	8.07	VA	8.40	VA	8.63	EA
4. It has light color inside	8.63	EA	8.53	EA	8.57	EA
5. It has dark brown edges	7.97	VA	8.43	VA	8.47	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.37	VA	8.45	VA	8.58	EA

Table 5. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 10 Grams Proportion as to Taste

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The ingredients used are rightly blend to the dinner roll.	8.87	EA	8.53	EA	8.57	EA
2. It has ideal taste of dinner roll.	8.03	VA	8.33	VA	8.30	VA
3. It has a lingering after taste.	8.27	VA	8.40	VA	8.17	VA
4. It has mild and unique kind of taste.	8.20	VA	8.40	VA	8.20	VA
5. It has acceptable sense of flavor.	8.27	VA	8.37	VA	8.27	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.33	VA	8.41	VA	8.30	VA

Based on the table, the Bakers, Consumers, and Sellers respondents rated the taste with an overall weighted mean of 8.33 which was interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), 8.41 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA) and 8.30 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 10g proportion in indicator 1 when evaluated by the Baker respondents is Extremely Acceptable. For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. For the Seller respondents, indicators 1 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. The rest of the indicators when interpreted were found to be Very Acceptable.

Table 6. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 10 Grams Proportion as to Texture

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The dinner roll with rice bran and malunggay leaves powder has fine texture.	8.80	EA	8.80	EA	8.23	VA
2. It has smooth texture.	8.10	VA	8.13	VA	8.23	VA
3. It has thin-walled surface.	8.13	VA	8.27	VA	8.47	VA
4. It looks presentable.	8.23	VA	8.37	VA	8.53	EA
5. The dinner roll with rice bran and malunggay leaves powder can easily cut into with the teeth.	8.17	VA	8.33	VA	8.23	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.29	VA	8.38	VA	8.34	VA

Based on Table 9, the Bakers, Consumers, and Sellers respondents rated the texture with an overall weighted mean of 8.29 which was interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), 8.38 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA) and 8.34 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 10g proportion in indicator 1 when evaluated by the Baker respondents is Extremely Acceptable. For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. For the Seller respondents, indicators 4 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. The rest of the indicators when interpreted were found to be Very Acceptable.

Table 7. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 15 Grams Proportion as to Appearance

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The dinner rolls with rice bran and malunggay leaves powder is inviting to eat.	8.93	EA	8.70	EA	8.67	EA
2. It is fluffy.	8.77	EA	8.53	EA	8.40	VA
3. It has a smooth surface.	8.23	VA	8.27	VA	8.23	VA
4. It has uniform shape.	8.13	VA	8.23	VA	8.17	VA
5. It has a rounded top	8.13	VA	8.43	VA	8.20	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.44	VA	8.43	VA	8.33	VA

The table shows that the Bakers, Sellers, and Consumers respondents rated the appearance with an overall weighted mean of 8.44, which is interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), 8.43 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA) and 8.33 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 15g proportion in indicator 1 and 2 when evaluated by the Baker respondents is Extremely Acceptable. For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1 and 2 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. For the Seller respondents, indicators 1 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. The rest of the indicators when interpreted were found to be Very Acceptable.

Table 8. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 15 Grams Proportion as to Aroma

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The dinner roll with rice bran and malunggay leaves powder have lasting smell.	8.90	EA	8.87	EA	8.70	EA
2. It has ideal aroma of dinner roll.	8.27	VA	8.50	EA	8.33	VA
3. It has a pleasant smell.	8.30	VA	8.37	VA	8.47	VA
4. It has a desirable smell for dinner roll.	8.37	VA	8.33	VA	8.27	VA
5. It has enticing aroma.	8.17	VA	8.43	VA	8.60	EA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.40	VA	8.50	EA	8.47	VA

Based on the table, the Bakers, Consumers, and Sellers respondents rated the aroma with an overall weighted mean of 8.40, interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), 8.50 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA) and 8.47 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 15g proportion in indicator 1 when evaluated by the Baker respondents is Extremely Acceptable. For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1 and 2 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. For the Seller respondents, indicators 1 and 5 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. The rest of the indicators when interpreted were found to be Very Acceptable.

Table 9. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 15 Grams Proportion as to Color

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. It has uniform color.	8.87	EA	8.70	EA	8.67	EA
2. It has golden brown outside	8.70	EA	8.50	EA	8.53	EA
3. The dinner roll with rice bran and malunggay leaves powder are visually attractive.	8.67	EA	8.47	VA	8.53	EA
4. It has light color inside	8.40	VA	8.47	VA	8.57	EA
5. It has dark brown edges	7.97	VA	8.57	EA	8.60	EA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.52	EA	8.54	EA	8.58	EA

Based on Table 13, the Bakers, Consumers, and Sellers respondents rated the color with an overall weighted mean of 8.52, interpreted as Extremely Acceptable (EA), 8.54 interpreted as Extremely Acceptable (EA) and 8.58 interpreted as Extremely Acceptable (EA), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 15g proportion in indicator 1, 2, and 3 when evaluated by the Baker respondents is Extremely Acceptable. For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1, 2, and 5 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. For the Seller respondents, all the indicators were interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. The rest of the indicators when interpreted were found to be Very Acceptable.

Table 10. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 15 Grams Proportion as to Taste

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The ingredients used are rightly blend to the dinner roll.	8.83	EA	8.57	EA	8.70	EA
2. It has ideal taste of dinner roll.	8.27	VA	8.53	EA	8.57	EA
3. It has a lingering after taste.	8.30	VA	8.37	VA	8.33	VA
4. It has mild and unique kind of taste.	8.47	VA	8.43	VA	8.53	EA
5. It has acceptable sense of flavor.	8.30	VA	8.43	VA	8.23	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.43	VA	8.47	VA	8.47	VA

Based on the table, the Bakers, Consumers, and Sellers respondents rated the taste with an overall weighted mean of 8.43 which was interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), 8.47 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA) and 8.47 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 15g proportion in indicator 1 when evaluated by the Baker respondents is Extremely Acceptable. For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1 and 2 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. For the Seller respondents, indicators 1, 2, and 3 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. The rest of the indicators when interpreted were found to be Very Acceptable.

Table 11. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 15 Grams Proportion as to Texture

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The dinner roll with rice bran and malunggay leaves powder has fine texture.	8.67	EA	8.80	EA	8.33	VA
2. It has smooth texture.	8.20	VA	8.23	VA	8.53	EA
3. It has thin-walled surface.	8.13	VA	8.33	VA	8.23	VA
4. It looks presentable.	8.40	VA	8.50	EA	8.67	EA
5. The dinner roll with rice bran and malunggay leaves powder can easily cut into with the teeth.	8.10	VA	8.37	VA	8.13	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.30	VA	8.45	VA	8.38	VA

Based on the table, the Bakers, Consumers, and Sellers respondents rated the texture with an overall weighted mean of 8.30 which was interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), 8.45 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA) and 8.38 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 15g proportion in indicator 1 when evaluated by the Baker respondents is Extremely Acceptable. For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1 and 4 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. For the Seller respondents, indicators 2 and 4 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable The rest of the indicators when interpreted were found to be Very Acceptable.

Table 12. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 20 Grams Proportion as to Appearance

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The dinner rolls with rice bran and malunggay leaves powder is inviting to eat.	8.77	EA	8.53	EA	8.37	VA
2. It is fluffy.	8.13	VA	8.30	VA	8.00	VA
3. It has a smooth surface.	8.47	VA	8.20	VA	8.23	VA
4. It has uniform shape.	8.13	VA	8.43	VA	8.07	VA
5. It has a rounded top	8.10	VA	8.27	VA	8.30	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.32	VA	8.35	VA	8.19	VA

The table shows that the Bakers, Sellers, and Consumers respondents rated the appearance with an overall weighted mean of 8.32, which is interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), 8.35 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA) and 8.19 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 20g proportion in indicator 1 when evaluated by the Baker respondents is Extremely Acceptable. For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. For the Seller respondents, all the indicators were interpreted as Very Acceptable. The rest of the indicators when interpreted were found to be Very Acceptable.

Table 13. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 20 Grams Proportion as to Aroma

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The dinner roll with rice bran and malunggay leaves powder have lasting smell.	8.57	EA	8.67	EA	8.67	EA
2. It has ideal aroma of dinner roll.	8.30	VA	8.23	VA	8.17	VA
3. It has a pleasant smell.	7.93	VA	8.33	VA	8.47	VA
4. It has a desirable smell for dinner roll.	8.30	VA	8.20	VA	8.33	VA
5. It has enticing aroma.	8.67	EA	8.27	VA	8.50	EA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.35	VA	8.34	VA	8.43	VA

The table shows that the Bakers, Sellers, and Consumers respondents rated the aroma with an overall weighted mean of 8.35, which is interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), 8.34 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA) and 8.43 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 20g proportion in indicator 1 and 5 when evaluated by the Baker respondents is Extremely Acceptable. For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. For the Seller respondents indicators 1 and 5 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. The rest of the indicators when interpreted were found to be Very Acceptable.

Based on the table 14, the Bakers, Consumers, and Sellers respondents rated the color with an overall weighted mean of 7.99, interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), 8.45 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA) and 8.58 interpreted as Extremely Acceptable (EA), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 20g proportion in indicator 1 and 3 when evaluated by the Baker respondents is Extremely Acceptable. For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. For the Seller respondents, indicators 1, 2, 3, and 5 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. The rest of the indicators when interpreted were found

to be Very Acceptable.

Table 14. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 20 Grams Proportion as to Color

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. It has uniform color.	8.70	EA	8.70	EA	8.60	EA
2. It has golden brown outside	7.63	VA	8.30	VA	8.50	EA
3. The dinner roll with rice bran and malunggay leaves powder are visually attractive.	8.53	EA	8.40	VA	8.70	EA
4. It has light color inside	7.50	VA	8.40	VA	8.47	VA
5. It has dark brown edges	7.60	VA	8.43	VA	8.63	EA
Overall Weighted Mean	7.99	VA	8.45	VA	8.58	EA

Table 15. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 20 Grams Proportion as to Taste

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The ingredients used are rightly blend to the dinner roll.	8.93	EA	8.57	EA	8.53	EA
2. It has ideal taste of dinner roll.	8.23	VA	8.30	VA	8.03	VA
3. It has a lingering after taste.	7.47	MA	8.13	VA	8.27	VA
4. It has mild and unique kind of taste.	8.37	VA	8.17	VA	8.13	VA
5. It has acceptable sense of flavor.	8.33	VA	8.40	VA	8.37	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.27	VA	8.31	VA	8.27	VA

Based on the table, the Bakers, Consumers, and Sellers respondents rated the taste with an overall weighted mean of 8.27 which was interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), 8.31 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA) and 8.27 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 20g proportion in indicator 1 when evaluated by the Baker respondents is Extremely Acceptable while indicator 3 was interpreted as Moderate Acceptable. For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. For the Seller respondents, indicators 1 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. The rest of the indicators when interpreted were found to be Very Acceptable.

Table 16. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 20 Grams Proportion as to Texture

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The dinner roll with rice bran and malunggay leaves powder has fine texture.	8.83	EA	8.53	EA	8.27	VA
2. It has smooth texture.	8.20	VA	7.80	VA	8.03	VA
3. It has thin-walled surface.	8.33	VA	8.10	VA	8.10	VA
4. It looks presentable.	8.20	VA	8.03	VA	7.63	VA
5. The dinner roll with rice bran and malunggay leaves powder can easily cut into with the teeth.	8.33	VA	8.30	VA	8.07	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.38	VA	8.15	VA	8.02	VA

Based on Table 21, the Bakers, Consumers, and Sellers respondents rated the texture with an overall weighted mean of 8.38 which was interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), 8.15 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA) and 8.02 interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 20g proportion in indicator 1 when evaluated by the Baker respondents is Extremely Acceptable. For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1 was interpreted as Extremely Acceptable. For the Seller respondents, all the indicators were interpreted as Very Acceptable. The rest of the indicators when interpreted were found to be Very Acceptable.

Table 17. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 10 Grams Proportion

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Appearance	1.82	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
b. Aroma	0.43	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
c. Color	1.34	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
d. Taste	0.52	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
e. Texture	0.37	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant

The table provides evidence that the assessments provided by bakers, consumers, and sellers regarding the acceptability level of MaBeanBran Dinner Rolls in 10 grams of proportion with respect to appearance, aroma, color, taste, and texture do not show any

discernible differences from the corresponding computed F values, which are below the critical F value. This suggests that the respondents' assessments are consistent.

Table 18. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 15 Grams Proportion

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Appearance	0.71	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
b. Aroma	0.66	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
c. Color	0.15	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
d. Taste	0.09	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
e. Texture	0.70	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant

The table shows that there are no significant differences between the respondents' assessments of the bakers', customers', and sellers' acceptability level for the 15-gram portion of MaBeanBran Dinner Rolls in terms of appearance, color, aroma, taste, and texture, and the corresponding computed F values that are smaller than the critical F value. This demonstrates how comparable the respondents' assessments are.

Table 19. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 20 Grams Proportion

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Appearance	0.44	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
b. Aroma	0.12	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
c. Color	14.52	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
d. Taste	0.06	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
e. Texture	2.63	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant

Regarding appearance, aroma, taste and texture do not suggest significant differences with the particular computed F values which are lower than the critical F value. Therefore, the respondents' evaluations are the same except for color.

Level of Marketability of Prepared MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in terms of Supply Availability, Production Cost, Consumer Demand, and Packaging and Labelling

Table 20. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 10 Grams Proportion regarding Supply Availability

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The ingredients used available all year around.	4.77	VHM	4.87	VHM	4.93	VHM
2. The product can be prepared and baked in a household kitchen.	4.37	HM	4.50	VHM	4.47	HM
3. Minimal amount is needed for the product ingredients.	4.33	HM	4.40	HM	4.47	HM
4. The raw materials of the product can be produced easily.	4.07	HM	4.47	HM	4.57	VHM
5. The raw materials is locally available.	4.43	HM	4.50	VHM	4.60	VHM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.39	HM	4.55	VHM	4.61	VHM

Based on the table, the Baker-respondents rated the production cost with an overall weighted mean of 4.39, interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM), while the consumers and sellers evaluated obtained a mean of 4.55 interpreted as Very Highly Marketable (VHM) and 4.61 interpreted as Very Highly Marketable (VHM), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 10g proportion in indicators 1 as evaluated by the Baker respondents as Very Highly Marketable. while the rest of indicators was interpreted as Highly Marketable. For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1, 2, and 5 was interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. For the Seller-respondents, indicators 1, 4, and 5 was interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. The rest of the indicators of the three groups of respondents were interpreted as Highly Marketable.

Table 21. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 10 Grams Proportion regarding Production Cost

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product is reasonable priced based on cost	4.73	VHM	4.60	VHM	4.67	VHM
2. The priced is affordable.	4.20	HM	4.63	VHM	4.43	HM
3. The cost is based on products value.	4.10	HM	4.40	HM	4.63	VHM
4. The price is suitable to the product's worth.	4.20	HM	4.60	VHM	4.73	VHM
5. The product is budget friendly.	4.20	HM	4.33	HM	4.63	VHM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.29	HM	4.51	VHM	4.62	VHM

Based on the table, the Bakers, respondents rated the production cost with an overall weighted mean of 4.29, interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM), while the consumers and sellers evaluated obtained a mean of 4.51 interpreted as Very Highly Marketable (VHM) and 4.62 interpreted as Very Highly Marketable (VHM), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 10g proportion in indicators 1 as evaluated by the Baker respondents as Very Highly Marketable. while the rest of indicators was interpreted as Highly Marketable. For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1, 2, and 4 was interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. For the Seller respondents, indicators 1, 3, 4, and 5 was interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. The rest of the indicators of the three groups of respondents were interpreted as Highly Marketable.

Table 22. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 10 Grams Proportion regarding Consumer Demand

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product is capable of supplying the need of potential customers.	4.87	VHM	4.73	VHM	4.83	VHM
2. The product nutritive content allows it to satiate the requirements and desires of potential customer.	4.23	HM	4.43	HM	4.63	VHM
3. Potential customer of various ages can purchase the merchandise.	3.80	HM	4.20	HM	4.30	HM
4. The product's organic components may have nutritional advantages for potential customers.	4.03	HM	4.47	HM	4.57	VHM
5. The product's organic components may have nutritional advantages for potential customers.	4.17	HM	4.33	HM	4.50	VHM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.22	HM	4.43	HM	4.57	VHM

Based on the table, the baker, consumer, and seller-respondents rated the production cost with an overall weighted mean of 4.22, interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM), 4.43 interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM) and 4.57 interpreted as Very Highly Marketable (VHM), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 10g proportion in indicators 1 as evaluated by the Baker respondents as Very Highly Marketable. while the rest of indicators was interpreted as Highly Marketable. For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1 was interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. For the Seller respondents, indicators 1, 2, 4, and 5 was interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. The rest of the indicators of the three groups of respondents were interpreted as Highly Marketable.

Table 23. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 10 Grams Proportion regarding Packaging and Labelling

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The brand name is unique.	4.73	VHM	4.83	VHM	4.87	VHM
2. The packaging is visually appealing.	4.27	HM	4.63	VHM	4.60	VHM
3. The product maintains freshness with its resealable top.	4.00	HM	4.47	HM	4.47	HM
4. The product appears original among other bread products.	4.13	HM	4.63	VHM	4.50	VHM
5. The style of packaging contains appropriate cushioning.	3.63	HM	4.13	HM	3.83	HM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.15	HM	4.54	VHM	4.45	HM

Based on the table, the respondents rated the production cost with an overall weighted mean of 4.15, interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM), 4.54 interpreted as Very Highly Marketable (VHM) and 4.45 interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 10g proportion in indicators 1 valued by the Baker respondents as Very Highly Marketable. while the rest of indicators was interpreted as Highly Marketable. For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1, 2, and 4 was interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. For the Seller respondents, indicators 1, 2, and 4, was interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. The rest of the indicators of the three groups of respondents were interpreted as Highly Marketable.

Table 24. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 15 Grams Proportion regarding Supply Availability

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The ingredients used available all year around.	4.77	VHM	4.87	VHM	4.73	VHM
2. The product can be prepared and baked in a household kitchen.	4.27	HM	4.43	HM	4.40	HM
3. Minimal amount is needed for the product ingredients.	4.10	HM	4.53	VHM	4.57	VHM
4. The raw materials of the product can be produced easily.	4.13	HM	4.40	HM	4.53	VHM
5. The raw materials is locally available.	4.50	VHM	4.43	HM	4.53	VHM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.35	HM	4.53	VHM	4.55	VHM

Based on the table, the respondents rated the production cost with an overall weighted mean of 4.35, interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM), 4.53 interpreted as Very Highly Marketable (VHM) and 4.55 interpreted as Very Highly Marketable (VHM), respectively. This

implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 15g proportion in indicators 1 and 5 were evaluated by the Baker respondents as Very Highly Marketable. while the rest of indicators was interpreted as Highly Marketable. For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1 and 3 were interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. For the Seller respondents, indicators 1, 3, 4, and 5 were interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. The rest of the indicators of the three groups of respondents were interpreted as Highly Marketable.

Table 25. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 15 Grams Proportion regarding Production Cost

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product is reasonable priced based on cost	4.87	VHM	4.73	VHM	4.83	VHM
2. The priced is affordable.	4.03	HM	4.27	HM	4.20	HM
3. The cost is based on products value.	4.20	HM	4.37	HM	4.50	VHM
4. The price is suitable to the product's worth.	4.23	HM	4.40	HM	4.37	HM
5. The product is budget friendly.	4.43	HM	4.67	VHM	4.40	HM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.35	HM	4.49	HM	4.46	HM

Based on the table, the respondents rated the production cost with an overall weighted mean of 4.35, interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM), 4.49 interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM) and 4.46 interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 10g proportion in indicators 1 was evaluated by the Baker respondents as Very Highly Marketable, while the rest of indicators were interpreted as Highly Marketable. For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1 and 5 were interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. For the Seller respondents, indicators 1 and 3 were interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. The rest of the indicators of the three groups of respondents were interpreted as Highly Marketable.

Table 26. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 15 Grams Proportion regarding Consumer Demand

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product is capable of supplying the need of potential customers.	4.67	VHM	4.87	VHM	4.83	VHM
2. The product nutritive content allows it to satiate the requirements and desires of potential customer.	4.27	HM	4.57	VHM	4.47	HM
3. Potential customer of various ages can purchase the merchandise.	4.13	HM	4.47	HM	4.43	HM
4. The product's organic components may have nutritional advantages for potential customers.	3.97	HM	4.40	HM	4.33	HM
5. The product's organic components may have nutritional advantages for potential customers.	4.00	HM	4.27	HM	4.40	HM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.21	HM	4.51	VHM	4.49	HM

Based on the table, the respondents rated the production cost with an overall weighted mean of 4.21, interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM), 4.51 interpreted as Very Highly Marketable (VHM) and 4.49 interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 15g proportion in indicators 1 was evaluated by the Baker respondents as Very Highly Marketable, while the rest of indicators were interpreted as Highly Marketable. For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1 and 2 were interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. For the Seller respondents, indicators 1 was interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. The rest of the indicators of the three groups of respondents were interpreted as Highly Marketable.

Based on the next table, the respondents rated the production cost with an overall weighted mean of 4.14, interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM), 4.51 interpreted as Very Highly Marketable (VHM) and 4.31 interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 15g proportion in indicators 1 was evaluated by the Baker respondents as Very Highly Marketable, while the rest of indicators were interpreted as Highly Marketable.

Table 27. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 15 Grams Proportion regarding Packaging and Labelling

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The brand name is unique.	4.73	VHM	4.93	VHM	4.60	VHM
2. The packaging is visually appealing.	4.23	HM	4.57	VHM	4.33	HM
3. The product maintains freshness with its resealable top.	3.93	HM	4.47	HM	4.30	HM
4. The product appears original among other bread products.	4.00	HM	4.43	HM	4.37	HM
5. The style of packaging contains appropriate cushioning.	3.80	HM	4.13	HM	3.97	HM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.14	HM	4.51	VHM	4.31	HM

For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1 and 2 were interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. For the Seller respondents, indicators 1 was interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. The rest of the indicators of the three groups of respondents were interpreted as Highly Marketable.

Table 28. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 20 Grams Proportion regarding Supply Availability

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The ingredients used available all year around.	4.77	VHM	4.83	VHM	4.63	VHM
2. The product can be prepared and baked in a household kitchen.	4.30	HM	4.30	HM	4.23	HM
3. Minimal amount is needed for the product ingredients.	4.00	HM	4.37	HM	4.13	HM
4. The raw materials of the product can be produced easily.	3.83	HM	4.30	HM	4.10	HM
5. The raw materials is locally available.	4.47	HM	4.40	HM	4.33	HM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.27	HM	4.44	HM	4.29	HM

Based on the table, the respondents rated the supply availability with an overall weighted mean of 4.27, interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM), 4.44 interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM) and 4.29 interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 20g proportion in indicators 1 was evaluated by the Baker-respondents as Very Highly Marketable, while the rest of indicators was interpreted as Highly Marketable. For the Consumer respondents, indicators 1 was interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. For the Seller respondents, indicators 1 was interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. The rest of the indicators of the three groups of respondents were interpreted as Highly Marketable.

Based on the table, the respondents rated the production cost with an overall weighted mean of 4.33, interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM), 4.48 interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM) and 4.45 interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 20g proportion in indicators 1 was evaluated by the Baker-respondents as Very Highly Marketable, while the rest of indicators were interpreted as Highly Marketable.

Table 29. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 20 Grams Proportion regarding Production Cost

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product is reasonable priced based on cost	4.60	VHM	4.73	VHM	4.57	VHM
2. The priced is affordable.	4.17	HM	4.37	HM	4.27	HM
3. The cost is based on products value.	4.07	HM	4.33	HM	4.33	HM
4. The price is suitable to the product's worth.	4.33	HM	4.40	HM	4.47	HM
5. The product is budget friendly.	4.47	HM	4.57	VHM	4.63	VHM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.33	HM	4.48	HM	4.45	HM

For the Consumer-respondents, indicators 1 and 5 were interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. For the Seller- respondents, indicators 1 and 5 were interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. The rest of the indicators of the three groups of respondents were interpreted as Highly Marketable.

Table 30. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 20 Grams Proportion regarding Consumer Demand

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product is capable of supplying the need of potential customers.	4.77	VHM	4.70	VHM	4.57	VHM
2. The product nutritive content allows it to satiate the requirements and desires of potential customer.	4.30	HM	4.53	VHM	4.33	HM
3. Potential customer of various ages can purchase the merchandise.	4.17	HM	4.43	HM	4.20	HM
4. The product's organic components may have nutritional advantages for potential customers.	4.90	HM	4.37	HM	4.30	HM
5. The product's organic components may have nutritional advantages for potential customers.	4.40	HM	4.53	VHM	4.40	HM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.31	HM	4.51	VHM	4.36	HM

Based on the table, the respondents rated the consumer demand with an overall weighted mean of 4.31, interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM), 4.51 interpreted as Very Highly Marketable (VHM) and 4.36 interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 20g proportion in indicators 1 was evaluated by the Baker-respondents as Very Highly Marketable, while the rest of indicators were interpreted as Highly Marketable. For the Consumer-respondents, indicators 1, 2, and 5

were interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. For the Seller-respondents, indicators 1 was interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. The rest of the indicators of the three groups of respondents were interpreted as Highly Marketable.

Based on the table, the respondents rated the packaging and labelling with an overall weighted mean of 4.21, interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM), 4.48 interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM) and 4.31 interpreted as Highly Marketable (HM), respectively. This implies that the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with 20g proportion in indicators 1 was evaluated by the Baker-respondents as Very Highly Marketable, while the rest of indicators were interpreted as Highly Marketable.

Table 31. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 20 Grams Proportion regarding Packaging and Labelling

Indicators	Respondents					
	Bakers		Consumers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The brand name is unique.	4.77	VHM	4.77	VHM	4.60	VHM
2. The packaging is visually appealing.	4.30	HM	4.43	HM	4.40	HM
3. The product maintains freshness with its resealable top.	4.03	HM	4.47	HM	4.40	HM
4. The product appears original among other bread products.	3.97	HM	4.50	VHM	4.23	HM
5. The style of packaging contains appropriate cushioning.	4.00	HM	4.23	HM	3.90	HM
Overall Weighted Mean	4.21	HM	4.48	HM	4.31	HM

For the Consumer-respondents, indicators 1 and 4 were interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. For the Seller-respondents, indicators 1 was interpreted as Very Highly Marketable. The rest of the indicators of the three groups of respondents were interpreted as Highly Marketable.

Significant Differences Among the Evaluations of the Three Groups of Respondents on the Level of Marketability of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll

Table 32. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 10 Grams Proportion

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Supply Availability	2.97	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
b. Production Cost	9.88	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
c. Consumer Demand	4.95	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
d. Packaging and Labelling	8.41	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant

As seen from the table, the evaluations provided by the baker, consumer, and seller-respondents regarding the marketability of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in the 10-gram proportion, as regards production cost, consumer demand, and packaging and labeling, exhibit significant differences. The calculated F values, all of which are less than the essential F value, clearly show this. This suggests that respondents' assessments vary for each of the aforementioned factors, except for supply availability.

Table 33. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 15 Grams Proportion

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Supply Availability	2.56	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
b. Production Cost	1.23	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
c. Consumer Demand	6.20	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
d. Packaging and Labelling	6.47	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant

The table reflects that the evaluations given by the bakers, consumers, and seller respondents in terms of marketability of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in the 15-gram proportion, specifically concerning supply availability and production cost, do not suggest significant differences. This conclusion is drawn from the computed F values, each of which is less than the critical F value. As a result, the evaluations of the respondents are comparable, except in the aspects of consumer demand, as well as packaging and labeling.

Table 34. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of MaBeanBran Dinner Roll in 20 Grams Proportion

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Supply Availability	0.67	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
b. Production Cost	0.98	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
c. Consumer Demand	1.57	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
d. Packaging and Labelling	2.76	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant

In terms of supply availability, production cost, consumer demand, packaging, and labeling, the table makes it evident that there are no significant differences in the assessments of the marketability of MaBeanBran Dinner Rolls in the 20-gram portion given by bakers, consumers, and seller respondents. This conclusion is based on the respective computed F values, all of which are smaller than the

critical F value. Therefore, it can be inferred that the evaluations of the respondents are consistent or identical.

Comments:

1. “The tastes of ingredients complement each other. It has a unique taste and flavor. Such a great product.”
2. “This dinner roll is for all ages. For kids, for teens and even for adults.”
3. “The 15g proportion is great in appearance, aroma, color, taste, and texture. The flavors of the ingredients are well blended and they complement each other. The 10g proportions, on the other hand is creamier than the two proportions but it is not as tasteful. While the 20g proportion, has too much flavor”
4. “This dinner roll is unique.”
5. “The product offers great cost-effectiveness when compared to other dinner roll in the market.”
6. “The 15g proportion have the most acceptable and it can compete with the other selling product.”

Suggestions:

1. The texture of the Dinner Roll with 20 grams proportion may still be improved.
2. The researcher may consider promoting this dinner roll as one product in the local market, school canteen, bakeries, and sari-sari stores.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn: The MaBeanBran Dinner Roll with a 15 grams proportion received favorable acceptance across appearance, aroma, color, taste, and texture from all three respondent groups. It shows great marketability potential due to supply availability, production cost, consumer demand, and packaging and labeling. The presence of malunggay leaves powder, mung bean powder, and rice bran powder is visually recognizable in the product, contributing to its health benefits given their nutritional values. Consumers can enjoy the MaBeanBran Dinner Roll while benefiting from its moderate carbohydrates, fat, and protein content, as well as vitamins A and C, Calcium, Vitamin B6, Iron, and Magnesium. Although the product has overall positive attributes, the packaging and labeling can be improved to enhance consumer appeal.

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